

Digital Depot – A Digital New-Media Art Preservation Tool

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Abstract

Our project addresses the ways and viability of preservation of born-digital art. We developed the Digital Depot software to edit and store the information about digital cultural heritage following the existing standards: the Spectrum collection management standard and the CIDOC-CRM ontology in order to facilitate the data transferability and reusability. The solution is aimed at NGOs and the artists' communities, to provide a tool to record the information that would be later available—from the technical point of view—also for integration into other aggregators and data collections.

Keywords

Digital archiving tool, standards, Spectrum-standard procedures, CIDOC-CRM ontology, group-sourcing, new media art archive.

Introduction

Digital Depot is an open software, and an online archive of Slovene new media art that facilitates data sharing in line with semantic web principles (10.5281/zenodo.18958405).

The key role of ontologies with respect to database systems is to specify a data modeling representation at a level of abstraction above specific database designs (logical or physical), so that data can be exported, translated ... For the Digital Depot software we have used CIDOC-CRM ontology version 7.1.3 (February 2024; ISO 21127:2023), i.e. the conceptual reference model (CRM) of the International Committee for Documentation (CIDOC) promoted in the framework of ICOM (International Council of Museums).

Our project adheres to the FAIR (meta)data and Open Science principles in the humanities (Research Data Alliance Metadata Standards Catalog, <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk>) for machine readable and machine actionable resources (<https://www.go-fair.org>).

The data in Digital Depot are exported as XML RDF (Resource Description Framework), as part of the W3C's Semantic Web Activity.

Connecting Spectrum and CIDOC-CRM

Digital Depot software connects CIDOC-CRM with the museum collections management standard Spectrum (Collections Trust). We stress the need to take into consideration, in addition to the data formats, also the museum practices and standards that guarantee the long-term preservation of cultural heritage.

The steps of the inventarization/accessioning procedure (inclusion of a new object into a museum collection, <https://collectionstrust.org.uk/resource/acquisition-and-accessioning-suggested-procedure>) consists of:

1. object number; 2. a brief description containing sufficient information to identify each object, or group of objects; 3. acquisition date; 4. acquisition method; 5. the source of the acquisition (donor or vendor); 6. entry number; 7. the transfer of title form number; 8. any conditions (or reference to any conditions) pertaining at the time of acquisition; 9. physically attach the number to the object (readme file etc. in the deposited folder); 10. photograph; 11. initial location of the object in the museum; 12. acquisition reason; 13. transfer of title date; 14. history of the object; 15. invoice etc; 16. additional contextual information regarding the object.

Figure 1 shows the mapping of Spectrum acquisition book (numbers in the diagram are the abovementioned steps) onto CIDOC-CRM ontology for new media artworks.

Figure 1. Mapping between Spectrum standard, as used in an accession book, and the CIDOC CRM ontology. ©NB&AV.

Figure 2 shows a relation: a new media artist/group created a new media artwork, which was referenced in a catalogue. It is expressed in triplets (entity → property → entity) and, when possible, people are identified by VIAF (<https://viaf.org/en>) and other entities with AAT identifiers (Art & Architecture Thesaurus, <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat>). It is important to use the existing, widely used and persistent identifiers. We have decided to include also the Slovenian Co-operative Online Bibliographic System & Services (COBISS) book IDs.

Figure 3 shows a visual graph of a new media artwork as entered in Digital Depot. Figure 4 shows the interface.

New media artist (= has created an artwork that is referred to by a relevant document)

Figure 2. The CIDOC CRM-based part of a graph that links a reference to a new media artwork and an author. ©NB&AV.

Figure 3. The CIDOC CRM-compliant graph in the Digital Depot interface. ©NB&AV.

Figure 4. Editing the graph in Digital Depot. ©NB&AV.

ID	Label	Author	Type	URI	Created	Last Modified
1
2
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Figure 5. All interactions with the graph (a CSV file). ©NB&AV.

The Digital Depot system also records all the activities of graph creation, which allows the later analysis and review of the knowledge-graph building process (Figure 5). This is important in

order to be able to access and review provenance of the edges and nodes in the graph, as well as archival material in general.

The Digital Cultural Heritage Preservation and the Art Community

The care for the data remains an open question and it needs to be addressed by the data storage providers in a way that is viable for the art community; for us the key issue was to make it possible to share the data using the RDF graph, i.e. an XML file. We are still tackling the question of the humanities scholars, such as curators, and the artists themselves using the CIDOC-CRM as a formal language to record the cultural contents. On the other hand we have seen that this ontology is either a core or a target standard in current semantic-web endeavors in the domain of cultural-heritage institutions, which is an argument in favor of the recording of information in this form. The Spectrum standard is used as a supplement, to support the creation of the inventory of a collection. The Digital Depot software also allows one to store the actual files on local servers.

Art Community and Self-Archiving

By making the Digital Depot an open software we aim to provide the Slovenian new-media artists with the tools and protocols to record their own art production following the relevant data-sharing standards. Our tool will empower the creators and at the same time capture the personal recollections and understandings of the developments of new media art. The collected datasets in the form of knowledge graphs will be unique assets for the humanities research.

The datasets will belong to and be controlled by the participants who may share them (partially, or in full). The goal is to organize an autonomous ecosystem of data management for the new-media art domain. The project will provide the expertise and technical infrastructure, as well as the export of complete data graphs for migration. In addition to technical solution we will provide support for understanding authors' rights management.

Acknowledgements

The *Sustainable Preservation of the Slovenian New Media Art* project funded by the Slovenian Research Agency (J7-3158, 2021–2024).

Authors' Biographies

Dr. Aleš Vaupotič is a new media artist and theorist. He was director of the Museum of modern art in Ljubljana. His research interests include new media theory, literary scholarship, semiotics, and digital humanities.

Dr. Narvika Bovcon is a professor of video and new media. Her research areas are new media art and design of user interfaces, she focuses on innovative interfaces for exhibitions and museums.